

Reactive Extrusion Additive Manufacturing (REAM) of Carbon Fiber Reinforced Epoxy Composites

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Background

- Additive Manufacturing (AM) with thermosetting composites can enable fabricating complex-shaped structures with strong inter-layer properties
- Reactive extrusion AM (REAM) is energy-efficient and rapid

Research Goals

- Investigating the printability of a reactive thermosetting polymer with short fiber fillers.
- Developing an understanding of precursor properties (viscosity, shear yield, and filler content) on printability and properties of resulting REAM parts.
- Finding the optimal fiber content via modeling

Methods

Results

Ability of different formulation to retain shape

Thermal footprint of a carbon fiber filled part during REAM

Shear rate-dependent viscosity of EPON 8111 resin filled with fumed silica and carbon fiber

Fluent simulation showing shear rate distribution in a passive nozzle

Printed part

Degree of cure of 10 vol.% milled carbon fiber epoxy coupon at different locations

Tensile properties of REAM composites in the print-direction

Partial alignment of milled carbon fibers along the print direction and between the layers

Results

Tensile properties of REAM composite in print- and build- directions

- Composite Modulus (GPa) (red circles)
- Composite Strength (MPa) (blue asterisks)
- Aspect ratio (l/d) (black diamonds)

Analytical modeling to find optimal volume fraction of aligned fibers ($l_c = 350\mu\text{m}$)

Conclusions

- REAM is an ultra-fast and low-energy process.
- Fumed silica and carbon fiber (either milled or chopped) can effectively modify the rheological behavior of the resin, rendering it printable.
- A carbon fiber filled composite was successfully printed with a degree of cure at ~95%, using active mixing, and displayed robust inter-layer properties.
- The incorporation of carbon fiber notably enhanced stiffness, although the strength wasn't affected.
- Adjusting the fiber length, volume fraction, and alignment could potentially lead to substantial improvements in both strength and stiffness.